

POSSIBLE RECENT MARSQUAKE-INDUCED BOULDER FALLS ON MARS. Bivas Das¹, Tuhi S.², Harish³, Kimi KB⁴, Anil Chavan⁴, Sharini KS⁵, Thahira⁶, Aditi R⁷, Vijayan S⁴. ¹Department of Geophysics, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India, ²Department of Geosciences, Auburn University, Auburn, AL, USA, ³Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, USA, ⁴Planetary Sciences Division, Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad, India, ⁵Department of Earth Sciences, University of Western Ontario, London, ON, Canada, ⁶Department of Remote Sensing, Bharathidasan University, Trichy, India, ⁷Department of Geoinformatics, Anna University, Chennai, India. bivas015@gmail.com, vijayan@prl.res.in.

Introduction: Recent boulder fall activities on Mars indicate the planet's ongoing dynamic geological processes and that can be correlated with recently recorded seismic evidence [1,2]. The Seismometer (SEIS) onboard NASA's InSight Lander had recorded over 1000 seismic events including Marsquakes, meteoroid impacts, and airbursts in three years of its life span. Marsquake Services provides seismic phase arrival times for recorded Marsquakes. The possible latitude and longitude of the epicenter of those Marsquakes are determined through the calculation of back-azimuth and epicentral distance from 3-component seismic data. Previous study [1] mapped the recent boulder fall from 2007-2020. Interestingly many Marsquake by InSight detected post 2020. In this regard, in this study, we present a comprehensive overview of Boulder Fall Ejecta (BFE) observed on the Martian surface that could be triggered by Marsquakes.

Martian Seismic Data: Mars seismic data is available at InSight Mars SEIS data services [3]. The InSight Lander was equipped with a very broadband (VBB) seismometer, covering 0.01 – 10 Hz frequency bandwidth, and a short-period (SP) seismometer, covering a frequency bandwidth of 0.1–50 Hz with a very low expected noise profile, so that it can capture signals from marsquakes, meteorite impacts and local events like dust-devils or landslides. Seismic events recorded by InSight from 2019 to 2022, are categorised based on their frequency content. Low-frequency (LF) and broadband (BB) events, serve as the 'classical' Marsquakes akin to earthquakes, occurring at teleseismic distances and depths of 20–50 km. In contrast, signals from high-frequency (HF), very high-frequency (VF) events, are much scattered and of less constrained origin. Generally, it is observed that tectonic events have low-frequency content, while meteoroid impacts generate high-frequency seismic signatures. Although not as strong as on the moon, but intense scattering is observed in Marsquake seismic records, which reduces the probability of detecting clear P and S phases.

Fig. 1. Seismograms of marsquakes in CF region filtered between 0.2 to 2 Hz (Broadband Vertical Component)

Recent seismicity in Cerberus Fossae region: Figure 1 shows all the seismograms of marsquakes, had their epicenter identified in the Cerberus Fossae (CF) region. 10 low-frequency Marsquakes have been identified to be in the CF region. To find the location of these quakes, first back-azimuth and epicentral distance are calculated using three-component seismic data (broadband, sampled at 20 Hz). Reference Martian Seismic Velocity models [4] are used to calculate epicentral distances and Back-Azimuths are obtained using the Polarisation Analysis method. Keeping in mind the noises and scattering, uncertainties are also assigned with calculated BAZ and epicentral distance values.

The concentration of Marsquakes in the Cerberus Fossae (CF) region suggests a potential fault system in this area. Further analysis by Marsquake services reveals that Marsquakes in the CF region predominantly fall within the magnitude range of 2.9 to 3.8. We analysed ten Mars quake activity which are

Fig 2. Boulder Fall tracks in Cerberus Fossae region of Mars. Black arrows indicate freshly formed tracks and white arrows indicate faint tracks. The images are HiRISE.

recorded from 2019 to 2022. Low-frequency seismic waves on Mars can travel long distances as compared to Earth, so these low-magnitude quakes can easily trigger boulder falls in the nearby regions. Notably, the largest recorded Marsquake S1222a with a magnitude of 4.7, is situated in close proximity to the CF region but remains just outside of its boundaries. This finding implies a broader tectonic activity beyond the concentrated CF region. For each of these quakes signals, we obtained the epicentre and for each epicentre we derived the range of latitudes which will likely induce boulder fall. Along with the range of latitudes we used the HiRISE images to morphologically distinguish the boulder falls.

Boulder Fall Ejecta on Mars: Boulders descending and leaving tracks are commonly seen on Mars [1]. These occurrences suggest recent instances of material movement on Mars. They are widespread on steep terrain, and the areas with numerous tracks have been linked to suggesting ongoing seismic activity [4], offering an understanding of internal processes. Boulder falls on Mars is an ongoing process as indicated by recent temporal HiRISE images. A recent investigation reveals tracks from Boulder Falls on Mars, amounting to a combined length of ~900 km as of 2020. Of these tracks, ~ 30% are found in the Cerberus Fossae region, indicating that this area is among the most seismically active regions on Mars [3]. In this work, we used HiRISE images to identify the tracks formed by boulders post to 2020. Comprehensive multitemporal HiRISE image analysis revealed all new boulder falls have ejecta along the track. We observed both fresh and faint tracks, however, no temporal boulder fall tracks were observed due to a lack of temporal HiRISE images. Fig. 2 shows an example of fresh and faint tracks observed in the Cerberus Fossae region of Mars.

The individual boulder bounces produce ejecta along its track and their freshness is one clue to indicate the recent activity. Within these identified 10 quakes around the Cerberus Fossae region, the possible recent boulder falls are examined. Interestingly we found several BFE tracks within the close vicinity to these locations. These tracks are observed in the vicinity of seismic events and are likely triggered by Marsquakes. Fig 2(a,b) both are very nearby locations, whereas 2a BFE tracks are relatively fresh than the 2b. These two tracks are observed within the same HiRISE thereby viewing and illumination conditions are similar. Thus, the older and relatively younger BFE tracks fade over time. Fig. 2d represent the BFE track which is close to the S1222a event. Previous study [1] already mentioned that nearly 30% BFE tracks observed around the Cerberus Fossae region, whereas the recent HiRISE image analysis reveals that the more BFE tracks are even observed from the same region. The lack of temporal images of HiRISE over this region hinders the interpretation, the more number of BFE tracks substantiated that this region could be one potential place on Mars where recent quakes are inevitable. Further work is ongoing to study the occurrence of these tracks in the Cerberus Fossae region and how the occurrence of these tracks is related to the seismic events in the region.

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